

Seedling survival and photosynthetic rate of different genotypes. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Genotype	Survival rate ^a (no. seedlings/pot)		Photosynthetic rate at flowering (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	Photosynthetic rate at 3 days after O ₂ enrichment (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)
	Run I	Run II		
IET 4087	3/4		28.67	8.36
4105	—		12.01	4.19
5631	—		15.66	5.27
3852	—		14.44	5.62
5882	4/3		29.30	8.25
5887	—		21.14	7.15
5890	—		18.28	6.10
5897	—		16.30	4.19
6145	3/3		27.14	9.12
6205	—		17.21	6.15
6207	5/4		25.42	8.37
6208	—		17.25	4.15
6209	3/4		24.24	7.92
6212	—		14.16	4.12
6271	—		18.47	5.13
6658	4/4		27.12	8.67
5606	3/3		34.83	9.15
2812	—		13.28	4.19
Jagannath	4/5		23.71	7.67
Pankaj	3/4		18.17	4.89
Intan	—		13.60	4.14
RPW4-14	—		21.39	7.12
Vijaya	5/4		29.58	8.36
T141	5/5		26.22	8.65
CR 1014	—		15.23	7.18
IR8	4/5		25.16	8.91

^a — = nil survival. Total number of seedlings/pot = 10.

survived better because their photorespiration rate was lower and their net photosynthetic efficiency was greater.

This technique helps in rapidly identifying promising rice cultivars that are efficient in photosynthesis. It is easier to

use and less cumbersome than the low carbon dioxide concentration techniques normally used to identify photosynthetically efficient plants. Large-scale screening is tried at CRRI and results are being confirmed. ■

Morphological evidence of air passages between culms and roots in rice

S. Y. Zee, Botany Department, University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

The mechanism of oxygen transport from shoot to root in the rice plant has been assumed to be associated with the passive diffusion of air through air passages in the tissue. If this view is correct, then it is important that such an air passage, which would allow the free transport of air from the top of the plant to the roots, be demonstrated.

Numerous studies have shown that lysigenous spaces and aerenchyma intercellular spaces are present in the cortical tissues of the rice plant culm. Similar lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces

are also present in the roots. The literature shows that these lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces may be responsible for the passive transport of air in the plant. But what is not certain is whether the lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces in the culm are connected in any way with the lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces of the root.

A longitudinal section cut through the junction point between the culm and the root (Fig. 1) shows that between the cortex and the central vascular tissues of the culm there is a band of sclerenchymatous tissue, about 0.1 mm thick (Fig. 2). This thick layer of sclerenchymatous tissue could act as a barrier, if not totally stop, the passive flow of air between shoot and root.

To see if this layer of sclerenchymatous tissue would act as a barrier to the

1. The outer appearance of the rice plant (variety IR36) at the junction point between the root (R) and the culm. L = leaf sheath.

2. A longitudinal view of the rice plant at the junction point between the culm (C) and the root (R). Arrow indicates the position of the layer of the sclerenchymatous tissue.

3. Longitudinal section through the junction point between the culm and the root (R). Note that the continuity of the layer of the sclerenchymatous tissue (S) has been interrupted (arrow) by the aerenchymatous tissue (A). ×100.

4. Another view of the region similar to that shown in Figure 3. Note that in addition to the aerenchymatous tissue (A), the vascular tissue (V) also passes through the interrupted region (arrow). S = sclerenchymatous tissue. × 100.

5. A higher magnification view of the interrupted region in the sclerenchymatous tissue (S). X 250.

6. Diagram showing the Passage of air (arrows) through the interrupted regions of the sclerenchymatous tissue at the junction point between culm and roots.

free flow of air, the junction points between the culm and the root were examined with the use of serial glycol methacrylate sections. The sections show that the layer of sclerenchymatous tissue is not continuous, but is interrupted at places by aerenchymatous cells (Fig. 3, 4, and 5) with large intercellular spaces. Within these intercellular spaces or "air passages," air coming from the shoot could easily diffuse as depicted diagrammatically in Figure 6.

Thus, morphologically, there are continuous "air passages" from the culm to the root in the rice plant. ■

Leaf rolling and unrolling behavior in relation to soil moisture tension and climatic factors

A. R. Gomosta, senior scientific officer;
F. A. Begum, scientific officer; and
M. Z. Hoque, head, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Rolling and unrolling of rice leaves are common symptoms of drought. The leaves remain open in the morning, roll severely at noon, then unroll in the afternoon. This behavior in relation to soil moisture stress and climatic factors was investigated under field and greenhouse conditions.

Nine pure line rice varieties belonging to the aus group (local early varieties grown as dryland broadcast paddy) were grown under dryland conditions in the field in March 1979 for 30 days with proper irrigation, then the water supply was stopped to expose them to high soil moisture tension (SMT). The SMT was measured by gypsum blocks at 8-10 cm and 12-15 cm soil depths. The degree of leaf rolling and water saturation deficit (WSD) and SMT were recorded when the varietal differences in terms of leaf rolling became distinct at noon.

All the varieties had no to slight symptoms of leaf rolling in the morning and in the afternoon. But at noon, they differed significantly in degree of leaf rolling even though the SMT during morning, noon, and afternoon was similar (see table). It appeared that the

Soil moisture tension at 3 different times measured by gypsum blocks installed at two soil depths, Bangladesh.

Soil depth (cm)	Gypsum block no.	Soil moisture tension (bars) at		
		0830 h	1230 h	1730 h
8-10	1	-6	-6	-6
	2	-2	-2	-3
	3	-2	-2	-2
	4	-1	-1	-1
	5	-3	-3	-3
12-15	1	-1.5	-1.8	-1.8
	2	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8
	3	-1.5	-1.5	-1.5
	4	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3
	5	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0

degree of the plant's internal moisture stress determined the rolling and unrolling of rice leaves in the field. The WSD percentage of rice leaves was considered the index of the plant's internal moisture stress, and was positively associated with degree of leaf rolling (see figure).

During the time of observation, the air temperature was 25°C in the morning and 35°C at noon and in the afternoon. Relative humidity was 98% in the morning, 53% at noon, and 43% in the afternoon. Solar radiation was 0.37 cal/cm² per minute in the morning, 1.00 cal/cm² per minute at noon and 0.25 cal/cm² per minute in the afternoon. The observations indicate that the amount of available solar radiation is perhaps the most important factor determining the WSD of rice leaves and, consequently, the degree of leaf rolling.

To quantify the contribution of solar radiation, temperature, and relative

Relationship between degree of leaf rolling and water saturation deficit (%). Leaf rolling scale: 1 = none or slight symptom, 5 = severely rolled.

humidity to WSD of rice leaves, the diurnal change of WSD of the three upper leaves of BR8 was determined under high SMT in the greenhouse from 0600 to 1800 hours at 2-hour intervals. The solar radiation, temperature, and relative humidity were also recorded. The relationship between average WSD of the three upper leaves and the three climatic components is shown by the following equation:

$Y = 4.437 + 8.324 X_1^{**} + 0.087 X_2^{ns} + 0.018 X_3^{ns}$, where Y is WSD, X_1 is solar radiation, X_2 is air temperature, and X_3 is relative humidity. The value of R^2 was 0.97. The equation indicates that available solar radiation significantly determined the change of WSD in this experiment. The percentage contribution of solar radiation, temperature, and relative humidity